

AI4

eOSC

Final high-level architecture specification

Deliverable ID	D3.3 - Final high-level architecture specification
Work Package Reference	WP3
Issue	1.0
Due Date of Deliverable	31/08/2024
Submission Date	31/08/2024
Dissemination Level ¹	PU
Lead Partner	CSIC
Contributors	CSIC, UPV, KIT, PRED, LIP, INFN, PSNC, IISAS, MMIS, WODR
Grant Agreement No	101058593
Call ID	HORIZON-INFRA-2021-EOSC-01
Digital Object Identifier (DOI)	10.5281/zenodo.11485109
Website	https://ai4eosc.eu/

Funded by
the European Union

¹ **PU** = Public, **PP** = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services),
RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services),
CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

Prepared by	Reviewed by	Approved by
Álvaro López García	Saúl Fernández Tobías	Project Management Board
Amanda Calatrava	Marcin Płóciennik	
Lisana Berberi		

Issue	Date	Description	Author(s)
0.1	21/02/2024	Initial ToC	Amanda Calatrava
0.2	01/07/2024	Updated ToC, initial content coming from D3.2 and assigned contributors	Amanda Calatrava
0.3	09/07/2024	Updated system and component diagrams with latest versions from GitHub public repository	Amanda Calatrava Álvaro López García
0.4	30/07/2024	Updated deliverable contents to reflect current architecture	Álvaro López García
0.5	31/07/2024	Updated the Requirements overview table; Add MLOps as a runtime component; Add drift detection scenario	Lisana Berberi
0.6	31/07/2024	Updated diagrams and architecture decision records	Álvaro López García
0.7	01/08/2024	Updated catalogue of services, final diagrams	Álvaro López García
	05/06/2024	First review	Saúl Fernández Tobías
0.8	07/06/2024	First review changes	Álvaro López García
1.0	29/08/2024	Final version	Álvaro López García

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. Introduction and goals	4
1.1 - Document structure and notation.....	4
1.2 - Goals	6
1.3 - Requirements overview	6
1.4 - Quality goals	6
1.5 – Stakeholders	7
2. Constraints	8
3. Context and Scope	10
4. Solution strategy.....	14
5. Architecture diagrams.....	18
5.1 - Container view.....	18
5.2 - Runtime view	20
5.3 - Deployment view.....	26
5.4 - Architecture decisions.....	28
6. Risks and technical debt.....	34
7. Catalogue of services.....	34
7.1 - Available services	34
Abbreviations.....	44

1. INTRODUCTION AND GOALS

The AI4EOSC project aims to provide a set of advanced services specifically tailored to the development of Artificial Intelligence (AI), Machine Learning (ML) and Deep Learning (DL) models and applications within the European Open Science Cloud.

The architecture described in this deliverable is a revised version of the one presented in [D3.2 - Initial High Level Architecture](#)². The live version of the Architecture document is found in the [AI4EOSC Confluence Page](#)³, under the [High-level architecture specification](#)⁴ document.

1.1 - DOCUMENT STRUCTURE AND NOTATION

As D3.2, this structure is based on the [arc42](#) architecture template⁵, a lightweight architecture description and documentation template aimed at delivering clear, understandable, simple and effective architecture documents.

The architecture notation and diagrams follow the [C4 model](#)⁶, a lightweight approach to visualize and diagram software architectures. C4 provides an abstraction-first approach providing guidelines to ensure that architecture documents are understandable, regardless of the chosen notation. The model is based on a hierarchy of abstractions, each of them corresponding to a different level in the system: a **software system** is made up of one or more **containers** (applications and data stores, not to be confused with the term used for operating system level virtualization), each of which contains one or more **components**, which in turn are implemented by one or more **code elements**. In order to visualise this hierarchy, one must define a collection of **Context (i.e. systems interacting with each other)**, **Containers**, **Components**, and **Code** diagrams.

The AI4EOSC architecture diagrams includes the following main visualisations:

- **System Landscape diagram:** This diagram provides a set of related systems and how they interact with each other, showing dependencies with external entities and the user relations.

² <https://zenodo.org/records/7728882>

³ <https://confluence.ifca.es/display/AI4/AI4EOSC+Home>

⁴ <https://confluence.ifca.es/display/AI4/High-level+architecture+specification>

⁵ <https://arc42.org/>

⁶ <https://c4model.com/>

- **System Context diagrams:** These diagrams describe how a specific system fits in the overall landscape.
- **Container diagrams:** These diagrams provide a view on how one system is built up on several containers.
- **Component diagrams:** These diagrams decompose each container further, showing the major structural blocks and interactions. For simplicity, these diagrams are not included in the deliverable, but are shown on the online version.

Moreover, we have also developed additional visualisations, in order to provide a better view of the architecture, the user interactions and the production deployment of the systems:

- **Dynamic diagram:** This will be used in the “Runtime view” section of this document, providing a view of how the different C4 containers work together in order to complete a user action.
- **Deployment diagram:** Used in the “Deployment view” section of this document, in order to provide a vision of how the software systems and its C4 containers are deployed and mapped to the underlying infrastructure.

The AI4EOSC C4 model diagrams are automatically generated using the [Structurizr Domain Specific Language \(DSL\)](#)⁷, with an online version of the updated diagrams in the following links:

- Diagrams, in a browseable and online live version:
<https://structurizr.com/share/73873/2f769b91-f208-41b0-b79f-5e196435bdb1>
- Code (DSL):
<https://github.com/AI4EOSC/ai4-architecture>
<https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.13343446>

Although the diagrams are included in the current document, the reader is advised to visualize them in the online and live version whenever possible, in order to be able to properly navigate through all the existing drawings and interactions.

Finally, the document also contains information regarding the project’s catalogue of services. This catalogue details all the services offered by the AI4EOSC consortium, with information about its value proposition, target customer base, service description, relevant technical specifications, etc.

⁷ <https://github.com/structurizr>

1.2 - GOALS

The aim of the AI4EOSC “Artificial Intelligence for the European Open Science Cloud” is to deliver an enhanced set of services for the development of Artificial Intelligence, Machine Learning and Deep Learning models and applications in the EOSC. The project is focused on enhancing existing services in the EOSC marketplace (i.e. the DEEP-Hybrid-DataCloud platform) and its services will make use of advanced features such as distributed, federated and split learning; provenance metadata; event-driven data processing services or provisioning of ML/AI services based on serverless computing.

The vision of the AI4EOSC project is to increase the service offer in the EU landscape by expanding the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) ecosystem to support the effective utilization of state-of-the-art AI techniques by the research community. AI4EOSC will strive also to provide an easy entry point for non technological users, resulting in an effective usage of pan-European distributed e-Infrastructures.

1.3 - REQUIREMENTS OVERVIEW

The AI4EOSC requirements were initially tracked in the "[D6.1 Analysis of user applications, collection of requirements](#)"⁸, being updated as needed in the online versions of the user tracking documents. At the time of writing this document, the complete list of 44 requirements from the three use cases defined in the project proposal is available in the "[AI4EOSC-RequirementsDB](#)"⁹.

1.4 - QUALITY GOALS

The main AI4EOSC architecture quality goals, at platform level, are aligned with the model defined in the ISO/IEC 25010 standard and include the following:

Req. ID	Description
RNF-01	Functional Completeness: The system provides functions that cover all of the specified tasks and user objectives.
RNF-02	Availability and maturity: The system is operational, accessible and reliable.
RNF-03	Recoverability: The system can recover data in the event of an interruption or failure.

⁸ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7635452>

⁹ <https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1wFe3YKH3hZTegTwaQR8rFh-6dIFy6-G/edit#gid=224085165>

Req. ID	Description
RNF-04	Operability: The system is easy to operate and control by platform operators and resource providers.
RNF-05	Compatibility: The system is compatible with existent technologies, standards and community best practices.
RNF-06	Functional Suitability: The system fulfils the user and operator expectations, in terms of completeness, correctness and appropriateness.
RNF-07	Performance Efficiency: The system only consumes the resources needed, providing appropriate performance for each case.
RNF-08	Time behavior: The system provides an adequate response time to the user interactions.
RNF-09	User Interface Aesthetics: The system provides a pleasant user interface, easy to use.

1.5 – STAKEHOLDERS

Stakeholder	Expectations
EOSC users	These stakeholders represent the primary users of the AI4EOSC platform, who expect to have access to a wide range of resources and tools for scientific research and innovation. They expect the platform to be user-friendly, secure, and reliable, providing seamless access to the resources they need.
Platform operators	The platform operators are responsible for ensuring the AI4EOSC platform meets the expectations of its users. They expect to have the necessary technical infrastructure and resources in place, and to be able to manage and maintain the platform effectively.
Resource providers	These stakeholders provide the resources that are used by AI4EOC users. They expect to have a clear understanding of their responsibilities and obligations, and to be able to contribute effectively to the AI4EOSC platform.

Stakeholder	Expectations
Research Infrastructures and e-Infrastructure managers	These stakeholders are considered as potential users (at a high level) and integrators of the AI4EOSC platform. As such, they need to understand a high-level view of the infrastructure, the technological requirements and the provided functionality, with clear boundaries and interfaces.
AI-on-Demand platform and AI4Europe project	Facilitator of European research and innovation in AI, with the objective to support all solutions and tools that contribute to the ecosystem of excellence and the ecosystem of trust, which define the European Vision of AI.
INFRAEOSC projects ¹⁰	The INFRAEOSC projects refer to the set of projects (either finalised or running) that are being funded through a series of competitive calls by the European Union, as a means to support the implementation of the EOSC. These projects are relevant stakeholders to join forces, search common areas and contribute effectively to the EOSC development.

2. CONSTRAINTS

The architecture described in this document is influenced by the following constraints, divided into technical and organisational at the EOSC level and conventions adopted by the consortium.

ID	Constraint	Explanation
Technical		
C-01	DEEP-Hybrid-DataCloud legacy architecture	The AI4EOSC platform is enhancing the DEEP-Hybrid-DataCloud (DEEP-HDC) ¹¹ platform, which already has an existing user base, as it is being offered in production through the EOSC portal. The new architecture must take that fact into account,

¹⁰ <https://eosc.eu/horizon-europe-projects/>

¹¹ <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2020.2964386>

ID	Constraint	Explanation
		providing a seamless transition between the legacy system and its evolution.
C-02	Data ingestion	Data can be stored on a system external to the platform. We should provide means to sync with external datasets.
C-03	Data locality	Data can be stored at a different location where the computing is available. AI4EOSC should take into account the cost of waiting for a task or transferring the data somewhere else.
C-04	Component deprecation	Some of the deployed components are being marked as deprecated by the supporting organisations (e.g. Mesos).
C-05	External components	Dependency on external components for the platform operations must be minimised, in order to avoid failures if external systems are down.
C-06	AI hype	Data Science, AI, ML and passing through a hype cycle that favours the sprouting of new components. Mature solutions, and those closer to the AI4EOSC partners, should be favoured.
C-12	AI Interoperability	AI Interoperability ensures that diverse AI models, systems, and components can seamlessly integrate and exchange information. To tackle this, AI4EOSC employs standardised frameworks, facilitating smooth interaction and compatibility across various AI technologies.
Organisational (EOSC-level)		
C-07	Distributed systems and operations	Federated and distributed operations are a must in the EOSC and the pan-European e-Infrastructures ecosystem. The design, architecture and underlying technologies must take that fact into account in order to choose the best solution in terms of distributed operations.
C-08	EOSC Interoperability	The EOSC Interoperability Guidelines, and the system-of-systems approach must be taken into

ID	Constraint	Explanation
		account from the design phases. Compatibility with the EOSC EU node and the EOSC core systems and services is mandatory.
C-11	EOSC Federation	The EOSC is envisioned as a system of systems, where the federation of components is a key element. AI4EOSC should engage with the EOSC EU Node and sister projects and relevant initiatives to effectively enable this federation of systems.
Conventions		
C-09	Open Source	All developments should be based on Open Source components.
C-10	Open API specifications	All APIs developed within the project will follow the OpenAPI specifications, with clear interfaces defined upfront.

3. CONTEXT AND SCOPE

The following diagrams start from the highest level of abstraction: the AI4EOSC System landscape (Figure 1) that depicts how the foreseen users (EOSC users/scientists, general users and PaaS Operators) interact with all the AI4EOSC systems (i.e. services) and the other EOSC systems. This diagram also shows the high level relationships for all the designed systems and the interactions between them. The following diagrams (Figures 2, 3 and 4) show the context for each of the systems, focusing only on them and without including additional interactions. A common legend is provided in Figure 5.

[System Landscape]
 Tuesday, July 30, 2024 at 11:10 AM Central European Summer Time

Figure 1: AI4EOSC system landscape¹².

¹² https://structurizr.com/share/73873/2f769b91-f208-41b0-b79f-5e196435bdb1/diagrams#system_view

[System Context] AI4EOSC Platform
Version: July 30, 2024 at 10:47 AM Central European Summer Time

Figure 2: AI4EOSC platform system context¹³.

¹³ https://structurizr.com/share/73873/2f769b91-f208-41b0-b79f-5e196435bdb1/diagrams#ai4eosc_view

[System Context] PaaS Orchestration and provisioning
Tuesday, July 30, 2024 at 10:46 AM Central European Summer Time

Figure 3: AI4EOSC PaaS Orchestration and Provisioning system context¹⁴.

[System Context] AI as a Service
Tuesday, July 30, 2024 at 10:46 AM Central European Summer Time

Figure 4: AI as a Service system context¹⁵.

Figure 5: Legend for Figures 1-4.

¹⁴ https://structurizr.com/share/73873/2f769b91-f208-41b0-b79f-5e196435bdb1/diagrams#orchestration_view

¹⁵ https://structurizr.com/share/73873/2f769b91-f208-41b0-b79f-5e196435bdb1/diagrams#aias_view

4. SOLUTION STRATEGY

The following table details the requirements gathered during the project lifetime, highlighting the decisions made to address each requirement, sometimes with a given requirement linked to different user stories. It should be noted that the requirements specified here relate to platform-wide functionalities. More fine-grained specific requirements are handled directly by each of the development teams.

ID	Requirement	Decision
Key Requirements		
UC1.Req01 UC2.Req04 UC3.Req04	Provision/customise the required computing resources to optimise the ML/AI training process	<p>Training complex machine learning models can be computationally intensive and time-consuming. In order to optimise the training process and achieve the best possible performance of the model, it is important to have the right amount of computing and storage resources and to tailor them to the specific needs of the training process.</p> <p>Designed three different components of the C4 model: Workload Management System, Training API, Compute Resources (offered from external Cloud/HPC providers as a software system) to fulfil this requirement.</p>
UC1.Req04	Programmatically retrieve prediction information from Model Inference	<p>Driven by the need to obtain insights and take action based on the predictions made by the model and to monitor its performance over time.</p> <p>Designed as an interaction between the OSCAR Manager component (in the C4 model part of "DEEP as a service" and the AI4EOSC Platform) [software system] to fulfil this</p>

ID	Requirement	Decision
		requirement.
UC1.Req09	Provide interactive development environment to develop AI models while having access to the necessary computing resources and data sources	<p>Enables data scientists, developers, and other users to interactively explore, experiment, and develop machine learning models.</p> <p>The IDE should be user-friendly and provide the necessary tools and features for the development and experimentation of machine learning models.</p> <p>Designed a separate component called “Interactive Development Environment” and added the respective relationships and interactions with other components, to fulfil this requirement.</p>
UC1.Req05 UC2.Req06 UC3.Req05	Train an AI model efficiently	<p>Driven by the need to reduce the time and resources required to develop and deploy effective models.</p> <p>One approach to achieving efficient training is to use parallel computing techniques, such as distributed training or GPU acceleration, which can significantly reduce the time required to train large models or get access to more resources to be able to train them.</p> <p>Grouped five relevant components to “AI4EOSC Training” with respective interactions to fulfil this requirement.</p>
UC1.Req07 UC2.Req11 UC3.Req05	Deploy ML/AI model inference as a service	Deploy a trained model to a production environment and host the model on a cloud-based platform, using a containerization technology such as Docker, or deploying it on a server or cluster.

ID	Requirement	Decision
		Integrated OSCAR as a component (in the C4 model part of “DEEP as a service”) to fulfil this requirement.
UC3.Req10	Try and combine different AI techniques (composite AI, Federated Learning)	Driven by the need to address complex and diverse problems that cannot be solved by a single AI technique. Designed the AI4Compose component as part of the DEEP as a service to provide service composition to fulfil this requirement.
UC1.Req14 UC2.Req08 UC3.Req09	Containerise the application(s)	Package and deploy an application in a consistent and reproducible way.
UC2.Req07	Enable secure access	Driven by the need to ensure that only authorised individuals or systems can access the AI system and the data it uses or produces. AuthN/Z based on GBAC using OpenID Connect.
UC1.Req02 UC2.Req09 UC3.Req07	Organise and track all training experiments	Developing an effective ML/AI model often involves multiple iterations, experiments, and adjustments to the model and its parameters. Keeping track of these experiments and their outcomes is important to understand what works and what doesn't, and to identify areas for improvement. Designed an experiment-centric dashboard, in order to keep track of all assets related to an experiment. Use state-of-the-art tools to keep track of data/model/code versions.
UC2.Req10 UC3.Req01	Publish and share results	Driven by the need to promote collaboration and knowledge sharing in the field of ML/AI.

ID	Requirement	Decision
		Designed the “AI4EOSC dashboard” container to fulfil this requirement.
UC1.Req13 UC3.Req11	Monitor the model and concept drift for the inference	Driven by the need to ensure the continued accuracy and effectiveness of ML/AI models in real-world settings. Designed the MLOps component and the dynamic views to fulfil this requirement.
UC1.Req03 UC2.Req05 UC3.Req01	Preprocess and prepare input data sets to be used for training and evaluation	Driven by the need to ensure the accuracy, effectiveness, and efficiency of ML/AI models. By properly formatting and cleaning the data, data scientists can reduce the likelihood of errors or biases in the model, and improve its ability to generalise to new data. Designed as an interaction between the “Storage system” and “AI4EOSC exchange” group to fulfil this requirement.
UC3.Req12	Provide metadata of a training dataset	The need to ensure the quality and consistency of data used in ML/AI models. Providing metadata can also help to ensure the reproducibility of ML/AI models by providing information on how the training data was collected and processed. Tool components like prov-fetcher , prov-viz , and prov-tracker have been developed to retrieve the provenance information.

5. ARCHITECTURE DIAGRAMS

In this section, we dig into the system and context diagrams presented in Section 3 to a more detailed view of each component of the architecture. Moreover, the section also presents the runtime views of the components, which describe the steps involved in the workflow of each of them.

5.1 - CONTAINER VIEW

The following diagrams include the AI4EOSC C4 Container view for the individual AI4EOSC systems: AI4EOSC platform, AI as a Service, and PaaS orchestration and provisioning (Figures 6, 7 and 8). A common legend is provided in Figure 9.

[Container] AI4EOSC Platform
Wednesday, July 31, 2024 at 11:17 AM Central European Summer Time

Figure 6: AI4EOSC Platform C4 Container view¹⁶.

¹⁶ https://structurizr.com/share/73873/2f769b91-f208-41b0-b79f-5e196435bdb1/diagrams#ai4eosc_container_view

Figure 7: AI4EOSC AI as a Service C4 Container view¹⁷.

¹⁷ https://structurizr.com/share/73873/2f769b91-f208-41b0-b79f-5e196435bdb1/diagrams#aiaas_container_view

[Container] PaaS Orchestration and provisioning

Figure 8: AI4EOSS PaaS Orchestration and provisioning C4 Container view¹⁸.

Figure 9: Legend for Figures 6-8.

5.2 - RUNTIME VIEW

The following diagrams include the AI4EOSS runtime view for different user and system interactions. Figure 10 shows the interaction for a user developing/retraining a new AI application and Figure 11 shows a federated learning scenario. Figure 12 shows the deployment of an application as a service. Figure 13 shows how to build a composite AI pipeline. Figure 14 shows how to automate the steps of deploying and monitoring AI models in production, whereas Figure 15 shows the drift detection scenario. A legend is provided in Figure 16.

¹⁸ https://structurizr.com/share/73873/2f769b91-f208-41b0-b79f-5e196435bdb1/diagrams#orchestration_container_view

[Dynamic view] Develop a model and register an AI4EOSC module
October, July 20, 2023 at 11:00 AM - User: Christian Guehen

Figure 10: A user developing an application, interacting with the AI4EOSC platform¹⁹.

¹⁹ https://structurizr.com/share/73873/2f769b91-f208-41b0-b79f-5e196435bdb1/diagrams#develop_view

[dynamic view] Federated learning scenario
Tuesday, July 30, 2024 at 10:46 AM Central European Summer Time

Figure 11: Federated learning scenario²⁰.

²⁰ https://structurizr.com/share/73873/2f769b91-f208-41b0-b79f-5e196435bdb1/diagrams#federated_train_view

[Dynamic view] OSCAR dynamic view
 Tuesday, July 30, 2024 at 11:10 AM Central European Summer Time

Figure 12: A user interacting with the OSCAR system to deploy a service²¹.

²¹ https://structurizr.com/share/73873/2f769b91-f208-41b0-b79f-5e196435bdb1/diagrams#oscar_dynamic

[Dynamic view] AI4Compose dynamic view
 Tuesday, July 30, 2024 at 11:10 AM Central European Summer Time

Figure 13: A user creating composite pipelines using AI4Compose²².

²² https://structurizr.com/share/73873/2f769b91-f208-41b0-b79f-5e196435bdb1/diagrams#AI4Compose_dynamic

[Dynamic view] MLOps: high-level automation
 Wednesday, 31 July 2024 at 12:33 Central European Summer Time

Figure 14: AI4EOSC MLOps implementation²³

²³ https://structurizr.com/share/73873/2f769b91-f208-41b0-b79f-5e196435bdb1/diagrams#MLOps_dynamic

Figure 15: AI4EOSC Drift Detection Occurrence²⁴

Figure 16: Legend for Figures 10-15.

5.3 - DEPLOYMENT VIEW

Figure 15 shows an exemplary deployment view of the AI4EOSC main C4 Containers in the current production platform. Note that some services are duplicated and some node relationships, systems and containers are not included for simplicity.

²⁴ https://structurizr.com/share/73873/2f769b91-f208-41b0-b79f-5e196435bdb1/diagrams#Drift_detection

Deployment Production
<https://structurizr.com/share/73873/2f769b91-f208-41b0-b79f-5e196435bdb1/diagrams#Deployment-001>

Figure 15: Deployment view of the AI4EOSC platform²⁵.

²⁵ <https://structurizr.com/share/73873/2f769b91-f208-41b0-b79f-5e196435bdb1/diagrams#Deployment-001>

5.4 - ARCHITECTURE DECISIONS

Important architecture decisions in the AI4EOSC project are recorded following the [Architectural Decision Records \(ADR\)](#)²⁶ and are stored alongside the [AI4EOSC architecture repository](#)²⁷. Apart from the initial project considerations, and taking into account the outputs of the “Platform feedback” study made by WP6 (c.f. Section 4 of [D6.2](#)²⁸), we can specify the changes made to the platform and how we solve the concerns of the users. Also, we have taken into account technological limitations that might have been found in WP4 and WP5.

The following table summarises the user’s feedback, as collected by WP6, that is relevant for the update of the AI4EOSC architecture. Please note that this table only contains relevant feedback from an architectural point of view. Other aspects such as documentation improvement, or user training, are explicitly excluded from it.

ID	User Feedback
Missing platform features	
UF-01	Image annotation tools.
UF-02	More computing resources and storage.
UF-03	Easy way to share the development environment with team members.
UF-04	Simple default GUI for modules.
UF-05	Tools to visualise training metrics.
UF-09	Data management tool.
Difficult platform aspects	
UF-06	Deployments may disappear or be reset.
UF-07	Resource restrictions (e.g. limited GPU size, memory, disk space).
UF-08	A bit non-intuitive: a lot of services, sites & options, difficult to get started.

²⁶ <https://adr.github.io/>

²⁷ <https://github.com/AI4EOSC/ai4-architecture/tree/main/dsl/decisions>

²⁸ <https://zenodo.org/records/10729328>

According to this feedback and the technical architectural aspects, the following table summarises the most relevant decisions, including links with the user feedback when applicable.

ID	Title	Context	Decision
0002	Remove Alien4Cloud	A4C adoption limited.	A4C has been removed from the architecture.
0003	Decouple orchestrator from training system	PaaS orchestrator generic API used to submit ML/AI jobs.	Provide specific training API, tailored to platform ends.
0004	Merge exchange and dashboard into a single component	Two different endpoints, offering similar information.	Homogenize into a single dashboard, anonymous views (marketplace) and authenticated views (training dashboard).
0006	Use OSCAR for the DEEP as a Service system	The current setup of the DEEP as a Service system is based on Apache Mesos and OpenWhisk. Mesos is a deprecated component.	OSCAR, a component managed by AI4EOSC consortium partners (i.e. UPV) will be used to provide a serverless approach for inference services.
0007	Replace legacy, unmaintained PaaS Components	Scheduling capabilities based on components that are not maintained anymore.	Replace unmaintained internal orchestrator components with new technologies.
0008	Utilise Nomad for the provisioning of the compute resources	Apache Mesos being used for platform layer is now deprecated.	Substitute with Hashicorp Nomad and related tools (i.e. Consul Connect, etc.).
0009	Use a single API endpoint for platform and marketplace	The previous architecture considered two API endpoints: marketplace and platform. –	Merge the two API endpoints into a platform-wide API: AI4-PAPI.

ID	Title	Context	Decision
		User Feedback: UF-08	
0010	Remove exchange and training database	The original architecture included two different databases in the design: the exchange database and the training database. – User Feedback: UF-08	Remove the database components but should allow for an easy switch in the API design.
0011	Reorganize exchange services	The original exchange design considered three different registries and repositories. – User Feedback: UF-08	Data is handled externally by the users, via dvc or other tools. Models will be handled externally. CI and CD are merged into a single component.
0012	Include other federated learning frameworks	Only Flower.ai was considered, but we need to broaden the scope of it.	Include NVFlare into the design. Expand a "Federated learning server" so that it can include additional frameworks.
0013	Include secret management system	Several AI4EOSC services require that the users provide a secret to interact with them. User Feedback: UF-03	Include a secret management system. Add routes in the API to manage them.
0014	Sidecar tasks	The underlying platform allows us to define sidecar tasks (i.e. tasks that run in parallel with the user tasks) providing additional functionality to the user tasks. – User Feedback: UF-08	Include a "Container" with the user job, so that we can draw the different tasks.
0015	Deploying CVAT in Nomad	There were two possibilities to deploy CVAT for users: deploy	Deploy CVAT as a standalone nomad job.

ID	Title	Context	Decision
		per-user CVAT, and deploy platform-wide CVAT. – User Feedback: UF-01	
0016	Use CI/CD enforcing platform level checks	The QA checks were configured via a Jenkinsfile that was stored in the user repo.	Define different jobs in Jenkins, including an AI4OS platform wide job, based on a global Jenkinsfile in https://github.com/ai4os/ai4os-hub-qa .
0017	Integrate DEEPaaS UI with Gradio	The DEEPaaS API provides a simple UI based on Swagger, not attractive for end-users. – User Feedback: UF-04, UF-08	Integrate Gradio and DEEPaaS API, so that the Gradio UI can be automatically generated.
0018	Integrate MLFlow with dashboard and secret management system	MLFlow requires that users register individually (OpenID Connect is not yet supported) and this requires an additional step. – User Feedback: UF-03, UF-05	MLFlow will be integrated with the secrets management tool, so that user secrets will be stored in it.
0019	Ease integration with storage systems	Users need to deal manually with NextCloud credentials when creating a deployment. – User Feedback: UF-08, UF-09	Register the API as a NextCloud client via its API, store generated credentials in a secret management system, and offer them to the users via a simple UI.
0020	Exploit sidecar tasks for data stage-in	Widely used open data repositories (e.g. Zenodo, Figshare) provide APIs to search for datasets and to	Implement sidecar tasks in the job allowing to download data based on DOI. Allow to browse

ID	Title	Context	Decision
		gather data. AI4EOSC users and other related projects are sometimes storing data on them, therefore it is desirable to provide an integration mechanism to download data into the platform. – User Feedback: UF-08, UF-09	Zenodo communities, as this is the most commonly used community repository.
0021	Integrate development environments with secret management system	Users need to define a secret for their development environments. This secret is hardcoded in the job. – User Feedback: UF-03, UF-08	Integrate the development environments with the secret management system, so that the secret is stored in it.
0022	Automate deployment and configuration of platform components	Including resources into an existing system or deploying a new one is not a trivial task. – User Feedback: UF-02, UF-06, UF-07	Deploying a new system, including new resources, scaling up and down should be automated.
0023	Gather platform level and user statistics	Users have difficulties to know how many resources they are using, or they have consumed. Reporting becomes a cumbersome and manual task. – User Feedback: UF-02, UF-07	Implement an `stats` endpoint in the API, and the corresponding view in the dashboard, so that it is easier to provide statistics. Implement tasks in the cluster to collect statistics.
0024	Node-RED integration to support AI	Node-RED appears as the most popular flow-based programming tool.	Adopt Node-RED as the main solution to support the graphical composition

ID	Title	Context	Decision
	pipeline composition		of AI pipelines, leveraging the execution of the inference phase to OSCAR.
0025	Elyra integration as an alternative to support AI pipeline composition	Jupyter Notebooks are one of the most popular options scientists use to develop and execute their applications. In this context, Elyra provides a pipeline visual editor for building AI pipelines in Jupyter Notebooks.	Support Elyra to compose AI pipelines able to launch the inference process in OSCAR.
0026	FlowFuse to support multitenancy in Node-RE	Node-RED is not multitenant. So, even if we can create user accounts, we cannot operate simultaneously in a single instance to support concurrent users.	Integrate FlowFuse as the best option to manage multiple instances of Node-RED.

6. RISKS AND TECHNICAL DEBT

The risk management strategy and procedures for mitigating any identified risks that may impact the project, both from a technical, domain, and managerial perspective are globally handled by WP1. Therefore, identified risks, together with its occurrence likelihood, severity and the corresponding mitigation measures are continuously monitored by WP1 and reported in the corresponding deliverables D1.1 and D1.3 (Project handbook).

7. CATALOGUE OF SERVICES

The AI4EOSC project has identified the following list of services, described in Section 7.1, as part of its public catalogue. An initial set of metadata is also provided for each service, with more comprehensive metadata being updated and maintained online in <https://confluence.ifca.es/display/AI4/Catalogue+of+services>.

7.1 - AVAILABLE SERVICES

Service Name	AI4EOSC Platform
Service Description	The AI4EOSC platform provides an easy to use toolbox to develop artificial intelligence and machine learning models in the EOSC.
Service Category	Compute, Storage, AI/ML, Analytics
Public URL	https://dashboard.cloud.ai4eosc.eu
Key Features	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Interactive user and development environments ● Federated and distributed model training, transparent e-Infrastructure access ● Metadata for model lineage and provenance ● Rich model metadata ● FAIR assessment of ML models ● EOSC repository and storage integration ● Automated dataset synchronisation

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Automated deposit of developed models in Zenodo and other repositories
Monitoring	Public monitoring of the platform and component status is done in https://status.ai4eosc.eu/
Documentation and Resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Documentation is available in: https://docs.ai4os.eu/en/latest/ Howtos and other more specific materials are also available: https://docs.ai4os.eu/en/latest/user/index.html#how-to-s https://docs.ai4os.eu/en/latest/user/others/video-demos.html
Support and SLA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> SLA to be agreed with final users. Offered generically on a best-effort basis. Acceptable Usage Policy (AUP) and Platform Privacy Policy are available: https://ai4eosc.eu/platform/acceptable-use-policy/ and https://ai4eosc.eu/platform/privacy-policy/
Contact Information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Contact details: https://ai4eosc.eu/contact/ Support via: https://ai4eosc.eu/support and ai4eosc-support@listas.csic.es Additional information available in the Open Science Cloud EU Node portal: https://open-science-cloud.ec.europa.eu/resources/services/eosc.ifca-csic.ai4eosc_platform

Service Name	AI4EOSC AI as a Service
Service Description	A platform for serverless event-driven data-processing applications that allows the deployment of AI models as services on a cloud environment, providing an accessible and efficient means to perform inference.

Service Category	Compute, Storage, AI/ML, Analytics
Public URL	https://inference.cloud.ai4eosc.eu/
Key Features	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Different methods of deploying services as serverless functions, short lived endpoints or on premises deployments. • Automated integration with AI4EOSC platform, with continuous delivery in place. • Integration with different storage systems.
Monitoring	Public monitoring of the platform and component status is done in https://status.ai4eosc.eu/
Documentation and Resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Documentation is available in: https://docs.oscar.grycap.net/ • Howtos and other more specific materials are also available: https://docs.oscar.grycap.net/training/
Support and SLA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SLA to be agreed with final users. Offered generically on a best-effort basis. • Acceptable Usage Policy (AUP) and Platform Privacy Policy are available: https://ai4eosc.eu/platform/acceptable-use-policy/ and https://ai4eosc.eu/platform/privacy-policy/
Contact Information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contact details: https://ai4eosc.eu/contact/ • Support via: https://ai4eosc.eu/support and ai4eosc-support@listas.csic.es • Additional information available in the Open Science Cloud EU Node portal: https://open-science-cloud.ec.europa.eu/resources/services/eosc.ifca-csic.ai4eosc_platform

Service Name	AI4Compose
Service Description	AI4Compose is a software suite designed to integrate and orchestrate various AI models and machine learning techniques into organised workflows. It supports visual programming tools like Elyra and Node-RED, allowing users to create and manage AI inference pipelines through intuitive graphical interfaces. AI4Compose is integrated with OSCAR for executing inference tasks, facilitating the incorporation of AI models into data science workflows with precision and efficiency.
Service Category	Compute, Storage, AI/ML, Analytics
Public URL	Node-RED (FlowFuse): https://forge.flows.dev.ai4eosc.eu Elyra (integrated in EGI Notebooks): https://notebooks.egi.eu
Key Features	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Visual composition of AI inference pipelines. • Integration with OSCAR to efficiently outsource AI model inference on distributed infrastructures. • Integration with EGI Notebooks. • Flexibility and scalability. • User-friendly interface.
Monitoring	Public monitoring of the platform and component status is done in https://status.ai4eosc.eu/history/flowfuse-ai-4-eosc-provider-upv-g-ry-cap
Documentation and Resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Documentation is available in: https://docs.ai4os.eu/en/latest/ • How to Node-RED: https://docs.ai4os.eu/en/latest/user/howto/ai4-compose/flows.html • How to Elyra: https://docs.ai4os.eu/en/latest/user/howto/ai4-compose/elyra.html
Support and SLA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SLA to be agreed with final users. Offered generically on a best-effort basis.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Acceptable Usage Policy (AUP) and Platform Privacy Policy are available: https://ai4eosc.eu/platform/acceptable-use-policy/ and https://ai4eosc.eu/platform/privacy-policy/
Contact Information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contact details: https://ai4eosc.eu/contact/ • Support via: https://ai4eosc.eu/support and ai4eosc-support@listas.csic.es • Additional information available in the Open Science Cloud EU Node portal: https://open-science-cloud.ec.europa.eu/resources/services/eosc.ifca-csic.ai4eosc_platform

Service Name	AI4 MLOps
Service Description	AI4 MLOps is a set of practices, tools, and services to manage and monitor AI/ML models in production. One component to support users in tracking of AI/ML experiments from testing to staging and to production, is MLflow. Self-hosted MLflow instance is provided as a central service for all AI4EOSC users.
Service Category	Compute, AI/ML, Analytics
Public URL	https://mlflow.cloud.ai4eosc.eu/
Key Features	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Central place for users to store AI/ML experiments, runs, and models • Self-registration AAI • User-friendly handling of experiment and model permissions
Monitoring	Public monitoring of the platform and component status is done in https://status.ai4eosc.eu/

<p>Documentation and Resources</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Documentation is available in: https://docs.ai4os.eu/en/latest/ • Howtos and other more specific materials are also available: https://docs.ai4os.eu/en/latest/user/index.html#how-to-s https://docs.ai4os.eu/en/latest/user/others/video-demos.html
<p>Support and SLA</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SLA to be agreed with final users. Offered generically on a best-effort basis. • Acceptable Usage Policy (AUP) and Platform Privacy Policy are available: https://ai4eosc.eu/platform/acceptable-use-policy/ and https://ai4eosc.eu/platform/privacy-policy/
<p>Contact Information</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contact details: https://ai4eosc.eu/contact/ • Support via: https://ai4eosc.eu/support and ai4eosc-support@listas.csic.es • Additional information available in the Open Science Cloud EU Node portal: https://open-science-cloud.ec.europa.eu/resources/services/eosc.ifca-csic.ai4eosc_platform

<p>Service Name</p>	<p>AI4 Templates</p>
<p>Service Description</p>	<p>The AI4 Templates Hub allows developers and users to create software project repositories, following AI4EOSC best practices and recommendations. These templates provide an easier path to integrate a module in the AI4EOSC marketplace, as they include all the required metadata and other code assets needed. The user-friendly web interface to generate new repositories is provided.</p>

Service Category	AI/ML, Analytics, Repositories
Public URL	https://templates.cloud.ai4eosc.eu/
Key Features	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Different template flavours, focusing on different user needs (advanced, minimal, child-module) • Easier integration of user developed modules in the AI4OS marketplace. • Web interface and API for effortless generation of software projects
Monitoring	Public monitoring of the platform and component status is done in https://status.ai4eosc.eu/
Documentation and Resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Documentation is available in: https://docs.ai4os.eu/en/latest/ • Howtos and other more specific materials are also available: https://docs.ai4os.eu/en/latest/user/index.html#how-to-s https://docs.ai4os.eu/en/latest/user/others/video-demos.html
Support and SLA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SLA to be agreed with final users. Offered generically on a best-effort basis. • Acceptable Usage Policy (AUP) and Platform Privacy Policy are available: https://ai4eosc.eu/platform/acceptable-use-policy/ and https://ai4eosc.eu/platform/privacy-policy/
Contact Information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contact details: https://ai4eosc.eu/contact/ • Support via: https://ai4eosc.eu/support and ai4eosc-support@listas.csic.es • Additional information available in the Open Science Cloud EU Node portal: https://open-science-cloud.ec.europa.eu/resources/services/eosc.ifca-csic.ai4eosc_platform

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The AI4 Templates Hub is based on the more general Templates Hub service: https://open-science-cloud.ec.europa.eu/resources/services/eosc.kit.templates_hub
--	---

Service Name	Platform Orchestration
Service Description	A set of microservices that allow access to distributed cloud compute and storage resources in a transparent and federated way.
Service Category	Compute, Storage, Cloud, Resource Management
Public URL	https://ai4eosc.cloud.cnaf.infn.it
Key Features	TOSCA-based deployment orchestration service on multiple IaaS. Cloud-oriented federation service. Ready-to-deploy user-oriented services over cloud IaaS.
Monitoring	Public monitoring of the platform and component status is done in https://ai4eosc.cloud.cnaf.infn.it accessible after authentication.
Documentation and Resources	References: https://baltig.infn.it/ai4eosc
Support and SLA	Support is given for the federated resources and related activities available within the project. Support for the deployment of user-oriented services is given within the scope of the project.
Contact Information	Support and information can be provided by INFN via the Distributed Systems Unit mailing list: ds@cnaf.infn.it

Service Name	Infrastructure Manager
Service Description	Infrastructure Manager is an IaaS tool designed to manage the creation of virtual infrastructures by deploying and configuring virtual appliances on different cloud providers, making infrastructures cloud-agnostic. It simplifies the process by making the deployment and management of the infrastructures automatic.
Service Category	Compute, Storage, Cloud, Resource Management
Public URL	https://im.eji.eu
Key Features	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Automation of virtualized infrastructure deployment and configuration with software installation. • Support for multiple Cloud back-ends. • Multi-modal access (Web-based application for user-friendly interface, command-line application for advanced usage and REST API for easier integration).
Monitoring	Public monitoring of the platform and component status is done in https://status.ai4eosc.eu/
Documentation and Resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The official documentation can be found here: https://imdocs.readthedocs.io • Video tutorials with demos can be found in the YouTube IM reproduction list here: Infrastructure Manager - YouTube
Support and SLA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Detail the support options available for the service and the Service Level Agreement (SLA) terms. • Acceptable Usage Policy (AUP) and Platform Privacy Policy are available: https://im.eji.eu/im-dashboard/static/terms.html https://im.eji.eu/im-dashboard/static/privacy.html
Contact Information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support tickets for the service can be sent through GGUS: https://ggus.eu/ assigned to the 'Infrastructure Manager' support unit.

- | | |
|--|--|
| | <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Software issue tickets can be sent to the IM GitHub Issues:
https://github.com/grycap/im/issues• Additional support can be provided via:
products@grycap.upv.es |
|--|--|

ABBREVIATIONS

ADR	Architectural Decision Record
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
AuthN	Authentication
AuthZ	Authorization
CD	Continuous Delivery
CI	Continuous Integration
DEEP-HDC	DEEP-Hybrid-DataCloud
DL	Deep Learning
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HPC	High Performance Computing
IaaS	Infrastructure as a Service
IM	Infrastructure Manager
ML	Machine Learning
FL	Federated Learning
MLOps	Machine Learning Operations
PaaS	Platform as a Service
SaaS	Software as a Service
SLA	Service Level Agreement
WMS	Workload Management System

